

A Review of Pediatric Antimicrobial Resistance in the Middle East: Trends, Challenges, and Strategic Solutions

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Abstract

Affecting mostly vulnerable populations, including children in the Middle East, antibiotic resistance (AR) is a current major threat to global public health. Although antibiotics are life-saving, their misuse caused a rapid spread of AR. This review describes trends in AR in Middle Eastern pediatric populations of Arab and non-Arab countries over the past decade. The assessment of AR patterns indicated that *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* are the predominant bacteria in Syria. In Egypt, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is frequently isolated, while both *K. pneumoniae* and *E. coli* were the most common pathogens in Saudi Arabia. Additionally, in Bahrain, Iraq, and Turkey, *E. coli* was the leading pathogen. Overall, *E. coli* is widely distributed across several countries, underscoring its importance in pediatric infections. The most common AR pattern observed of *E. coli* in various countries was to Ampicillin. This was notably documented in studies from Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Bahrain, Iraq, and Turkey, highlighting the prevalence of such AR type in these regions. The latest Middle East AR insights highlight critical trends and challenges threatening global health. This study aims to inform healthcare policies and practices, ultimately improving patient outcomes and decreasing the growing threat of AR in the Middle East and worldwide.

Keywords: Pediatric; AR trends; Middle East; Challenges; Strategic solutions

1 Introduction

Antibiotics, which are seen as miraculous tools in modern medicine, have revolutionized the field of healthcare since their discovery in the 20th century, significantly decreasing morbidity and mortality rates in both human and livestock populations.^{1,2} Nevertheless, the inappropriate utilization of antibiotics in human, animal, and environmental domains, along with the global transmission of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and resistance genes, has led to the development of bacterial resistance.³ Contracting infections resistant to antimicrobial agents results in severe illnesses and extended hospital admission, leading to an increase in healthcare costs and elevated expenses associated with alternative medications.^{4,5} Antimicrobial resistance (AMR), characterized by bacterial pathogens acquiring resistance to the effects of antibiotics,⁶ represents an urgent and escalating global health crisis that demands consistent attention and prioritization from all healthcare professionals and institutions.⁷

AMR has spread to every part of the world, affecting all continents and countries. In 2019, approximately 1.27 million deaths were linked to AMR.⁸ It is predicted that if this trend continues, AMR could lead to 10 million deaths annually worldwide by 2050.⁹ Furthermore, among the most vulnerable members of society, namely, children in the Middle East, the impact of antimicrobial resistance is particularly noticeable, as these individuals become particularly susceptible to AMR because of their developing immune system and frequent exposure to antibiotics. The region's high infection rates further contribute to this susceptibility.^{10,11} The region has observed instances of inappropriate antibiotic use and self-medication practices.¹² Antibacterial resistance presents major challenges for pediatric healthcare. Moreover, the development of new antibiotics has notably decreased in recent decades.^{13,14} Additionally, the effectiveness of existing antibiotics diminishes over time due to antimicrobial resistance.¹⁵⁻²⁰

The Middle East, which includes 17 countries, such as Saudi Arabia, Yemen, Lebanon, Syria, and Iraq, faces particular difficulties due to variables such as excessive antibiotic consumption, insufficient healthcare infrastructure, and restricted access to clean water and sanitation services in certain regions.²¹⁻²⁴ Additionally, conflicts and migrations of populations in the Middle East have contributed to the spread of resistant strains, making it necessary to understand the local dynamics of bacterial resistance in this region.²⁵

Although AR has been widely discussed globally, there is a lack of up-to-date systematic reviews focusing specifically on the epidemiology and causes of bacterial resistance in children in the Middle East. The present research aims to provide a comprehensive and up-to-date overview of the prevalence of common resistant bacteria among children in the Middle East by

combining data from the preceding ten years (2015--2024), which is essential for advancing our understanding of this critical public health issue.

2 Prevalence of bacterial infection among children in the Middle East

2.1 Overview of common bacterial infections among children in non-Arab countries in the Middle East

2.1.1 Iran

A retrospective study was conducted at the Children's Medical Center Hospital (CMC) in Tehran, Iran, a tertiary referral hospital affiliated with Tehran University of Medical Sciences. The study spanned a five-year period from March 2015 to February 2019 and focused on patients with positive blood cultures. Over this period, 3,179 cases of positive blood cultures were identified, yielding 2,824 bacterial isolates. Among these, 46% (1,312 cases) were gram-positive bacteria, whereas 54% (1,512 cases) were gram-negative. The most frequently isolated gram-negative bacteria were *Pseudomonas* spp., accounting for 17.6% (266 cases), followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, accounting for 16% (242 cases). On the gram-positive side, coagulase-negative staphylococci (CONS) were the most common, accounting for 53% (697 cases) of the isolates, with *Streptococcus* spp. accounting for 18% (237 cases). The study also revealed that coagulase-negative staphylococci (CONS), the most frequently isolated gram-positive bacteria, exhibited high resistance to penicillin. However, these isolates showed significant sensitivity to vancomycin, indicating their effectiveness as a treatment option against CONS infections in this pediatric population. Additionally, while the study highlighted the antimicrobial resistance patterns of several bacteria, it did not include resistance testing for *Pseudomonas* spp., leaving a gap in understanding the susceptibility of this significant gram-negative pathogen.²⁶ Furthermore, a cross-sectional study aimed to examine the incidence of uropathogens and their AR patterns in pediatric patients with urinary tract infections (UTIs) at Kashan Shahid Beheshti Hospital from 2019--2020. The study analyzed the medical records of pediatric patients, both male and female, aged one year and older. Among the 400 children included in the study, *Escherichia coli* was the most frequently isolated microorganism, accounting for 283 cases (70.8%). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the second most common pneumonia and was identified in 17.8% of the patients. Notably, the antibiotic ampicillin is associated with a significant proportion of *Escherichia coli*-resistant cases.²⁷ Another cross-sectional study was conducted on 8,908 pediatric patients suspected of having cystic fibrosis (CF) at the Tehran Pediatric Central Hospital in Tehran, Iran, from March 2015 to August 2017. Each participant underwent two sweat tests (via the Gibson and Cooke technique), and sputum samples were collected for microbial culture if both tests were positive for CF. Of the total patient population, 53 patients (83.6%) were found to harbor bacteria and fungi species, whereas 30 patients (16.4%) exhibited normal flora. Additionally, 7.2% of the patients were coinfecting with more than one species. Among the culture-positive patients, 85 patients (55.5%) were infected

with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, followed by 24 patients (15.6%) with *Staphylococcus aureus*. Antibiotic susceptibility testing revealed that *P. aeruginosa* isolates presented the highest resistance to gentamicin (11.7%), followed by amikacin (7.05%).²⁸ Additionally, a descriptive cross-sectional study was performed in the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) at Alzahra Hospital in Tabriz, Iran, from December 2016 to January 2018. Research has focused on identifying the pathogens responsible for neonatal sepsis, analyzing positive blood cultures, and examining antibiotic susceptibility patterns. This study involved a thorough review of the medical records of neonates, with special attention given to ensuring the accuracy of positive blood culture results, especially for coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS), by cross-referencing with clinical symptoms. If any inconsistencies were found, the blood cultures were retested for confirmation. CSF samples were collected via sterile procedures, whereas urine samples were obtained through catheterization or suprapubic aspiration. The study included all neonates either born at the hospital or referred to the hospital with positive blood cultures and clinical signs of early-onset neonatal sepsis (EONS) or late-onset neonatal sepsis (LONS). Neonates with congenital abnormalities or dysmorphic conditions were excluded from the study. The findings revealed that 174 neonates had positive blood cultures. Among these bacteria, gram-negative bacteria were more prevalent, with *Acinetobacter* accounting for 19.8% of the bacteria, followed by *Klebsiella* at 12.5%. The gram-positive bacteria included coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) at 35.2% and *Enterococcus* at 5.7%. Notably, *Acinetobacter* showed no sensitivity to ciprofloxacin, whereas CoNS had minimal sensitivity to cotrimoxazole and amikacin, with only 3.2% effectiveness.²⁹

2.1.2 Turkey

A study was conducted to identify the causative microorganisms in children under 17 years of age who were diagnosed with urinary tract infections (UTIs) at Kartal Dr. Lutfi Kirdar Training and Research Hospital in Turkey. Urine samples from 4,801 children were collected between January 2018 and July 2019. The bacterial cultures revealed that 89.4% (n=2,318) of the isolates were gram-negative, whereas 10.6% (n=274) were gram-positive. The most frequently isolated bacteria were *Escherichia coli* (67.7%), followed by *Klebsiella* species (10.7%). *E. coli* presented the highest resistance to ampicillin (66.6%), whereas *Klebsiella* species presented the lowest resistance to cefepime (48.4%).³⁰ Another study aimed to evaluate AR patterns in children with pyelonephritis. The study retrospectively reviewed 102 pediatric patients aged 1-17 years who experienced recurrent UTIs during an episode of pyelonephritis and were admitted to the Pediatric Nephrology Clinic over an 18-month period. A UTI was defined as the presence of a single bacterial strain with 10^5 CFU/mL in a midstream urine sample or 10^3 CFU/mL in a catheter-obtained sample. Among the patients, 56.8% (58 patients) had urinary tract anomalies. The predominant bacterial pathogen identified was *Escherichia coli* (73.5%), followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (8.8%). The study revealed that

bacterial isolates presented significant resistance to trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. However, no specific AR tests have been conducted for *E. coli* or for individual bacterial strains to determine their resistance to various antibiotics.³¹

2.1.3 Cyprus

There is currently no research on bacterial resistance among pediatric patients in Cyprus, a Middle Eastern nation.

2.2 Overview of common bacterial infections among children in Arab countries in the Middle East

2.2.1 Syria

Kahal et al. conducted two retrospective studies in a large Middle Eastern hospital to examine the epidemiology, culture results, resistance patterns, and outcomes in pediatric infections. The first study (2023) included 116 patients and 177 positive cultures, where gram-negative bacteria made up 64% and gram-positive 36%. The most common isolates were *Staphylococcus aureus* (33%) and *Enterobacter* (21%). High resistance was reported for nalidixic acid and norfloxacin (100%) in *Staphylococcus aureus* samples.³²

The second study (2022) focused on pediatric patients in Damascus Hospital during the Syrian crisis and COVID-19. It involved 117 children and 183 positive cultures. *Staphylococcus* remained the most frequent isolate, followed by *Enterobacter* (21%). Resistance rates of 53% were observed for cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, and trimethoprim against *Staphylococcus aureus*.³³ Moreover, Abbood et al. (2022) analyzed antimicrobial resistance in urinary pathogens from Syrian pediatric UTI cases. Among 48 urine samples, *Escherichia coli* (63%) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (25%) were the most common. Both showed resistance to cefepodoxime, cephalexin, nalidixic acid, TMP-SMX, cefexime, and ceftriaxone. However, *Klebsiella* had higher resistance to ciprofloxacin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, gentamicin, and nitrofurantoin, while *E. coli* was more resistant to cefotaxime, cefuroxime, norfloxacin, and imipenem. Amikacin was effective against all isolates (100%).³⁴ Jadeed et al. (2021) conducted a prospective study on carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE) in pediatric patients at Children's University Hospital in Damascus. From 277 samples (blood, urine, CSF, pus, catheters, etc.), the main CRE species were *Klebsiella* (51.2%) and *E. coli* (43.2%). Carbapenem resistance was found in 125 samples. CRE showed high resistance to cephalosporins (92.8%–99.1%) and penicillin (96.8%–99.2%), while lower resistance was seen for tigecycline (13.3%) and colistin (26.6%). Non-CRE isolates were most resistant to cefotaxime (82.2%) and ceftriaxone (82.9%), with low resistance to carbapenems (0%), colistin (7.2%), and amikacin (7.2%).³⁵ In addition, a study conducted at Galilee Medical Centre in Israel included 128 Syrian pediatric patients. Screening of 107 children for ESBL, CRE, MRSA, MDR *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and VRE found that 83% were MDR carriers. Among them, 78% had ESBL-producing organisms, with *E. coli* responsible for 95% of these infections.³⁶

2.2.2 Egypt

A study by Attia et al. (2023) at a pediatric hospital in Alexandria, Egypt, investigated the prevalence of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* infections among children. Among 142 culture-positive samples, 131 (92.3%) were single bacterial infections and 11 (7.7%) were mixed. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the most common single isolate (47 cases, 36%). Other pathogens included *Escherichia coli* (27%), coagulase-negative staphylococci (14%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (8%), *Pseudomonas* spp. (5%), *Acinetobacter* spp. (3%), *Enterobacter* spp. (4%), *Enterococcus* spp. (2%), and *Citrobacter* spp. (1%). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* also appeared in 8 of the 11 mixed infections, bringing its total prevalence to 55 cases (36%).³⁷ Antibiotic susceptibility testing of the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates revealed high resistance rates to cefadroxil, ceftriaxone, and cefepime (89.1%), ceftazidime (87%), ampicillin/sulbactam (80.4%), and amoxicillin/clavulanic acid (78.3%). Resistance was also high for piperacillin/tazobactam and gentamicin (76.1%), cefoxitin (74%), and aztreonam (73.9%). Resistance to carbapenems was observed in over half of the cases: imipenem (52.2%) and meropenem (56.5%). The highest sensitivity was reported for colistin (71.7%) and tigecycline (67.4%).³⁷

Hussein et al. (2023) studied pneumonia-causing bacteria and their antimicrobial sensitivity among Egyptian children. The study included 50 immunocompetent children admitted to Ain-Shams University Children's Hospital. Sputum cultures were obtained via cough swabs or endotracheal aspirates. Of the 30 children with community-acquired pneumonia (CAP), *Streptococcus pneumoniae* was found in 7 cases (23.3%). In the 20 hospital-acquired pneumonia (HAP) cases, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the most prevalent pathogen, isolated in 9 patients (45%). Antibiotic testing revealed that *S. pneumoniae* in CAP cases had the least resistance to cefadroxil, ceftriaxone, and cefepime (57.1%). In HAP cases, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* showed the least resistance to amikacin (33.3%).³⁸

A multicenter study on neonatal sepsis was conducted in three Egyptian hospitals: El Shatby University Hospital, Mabart al Asafra Hospital (Alexandria), and Damanhur General Hospital (El Behira). A total of 2,400 blood samples were collected from neonates with sepsis symptoms. Among them, 457 cases were culture-positive. Gram-negative bacteria accounted for 73.6% (336 cases), while gram-positive bacteria made up 19.6% (90 cases). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the leading gram-negative isolate (245 of 336, 73%). These strains showed 100% resistance to amoxicillin/clavulanic acid and ampicillin/sulbactam. Among gram-positive isolates, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Enterococcus* spp. each accounted for 30 cases (33%). *S. aureus* had 83% resistance to ampicillin, while *Enterococcus* spp. were fully resistant to cefoxitin.³⁹

A prospective observational study was conducted in two PICUs at Cairo University Hospitals examined gram-negative bacterial (GNB) infections over a one-year period. Out of 1,420 admitted patients, 291 developed GNB infections. *Klebsiella* species were the most frequently isolated organisms (36%), followed by *Pseudomonas* (30.1%). Quinolones and second-generation cephalosporins showed the lowest susceptibility rates against these infections.⁴⁰ Finally, a study at an Egyptian healthcare center treating children with cancer analyzed bloodstream infections (BSIs) and AR. The study involved 607 children aged 3 months to 18 years. Most isolates were gram-negative bacilli, with *Escherichia coli* (27.8%) being the most frequent. Among gram-positive cocci, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* was the most common. *E. coli* showed 99.2% resistance to ampicillin and 0% resistance to colistin. *S. epidermidis* had 100% resistance to benzylpenicillin but 0% resistance to tigecycline, teicoplanin, and vancomycin.⁴¹

2.2.3 Saudi Arabia

A retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics at King Abdulaziz University Hospital in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, from February 2019 to September 2021. This study included children aged 0-14 years. During this period, 1,056 patient files were reviewed, with 510 patients meeting the inclusion criteria. A total of 510 uropathogens were isolated. The most common isolated pathogen was *Escherichia coli* (54.5%), followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (20.6%). Antimicrobial susceptibility testing revealed that *E. coli* exhibited the highest resistance to ampicillin (71.2%) and cefazolin (56.5%). Among *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates, there was a 100% resistance rate to ampicillin and a 67.6% resistance rate to nitrofurantoin.⁴² Moreover, a retrospective matched case-control study was conducted on pediatric patients with carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE) infections at King Fahad Medical City between January 2016 and 2017. The study included children aged 17 years or younger. A total of 19 patients had index clinical cultures positive for CRE. Among these cases, the most commonly identified species were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (47.4%; n=9) and *Escherichia coli* (31.6%; n=6), along with other prevalent species.⁴³ A retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted on pediatric patients under 18 years of age who were admitted to King Abdulaziz University Hospital between October 2021 and November 2022. This study focused on patients with confirmed bacterial infections from blood or body fluids. To ensure accurate data interpretation, patients with fungal, mycobacterial tuberculosis, or protozoal infections were excluded. The study included 88 patients: 23 neonates, 27 infants, 30 children, and 8 adolescents. Among the 1,749 cultures performed, 441 were positive for bacterial isolates. Multidrug-resistant bacteria were detected in 223 of the total cultures (12.8%), and 223 of the positive cultures (54.3%) were positive. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was the most frequently isolated organism, appearing in 122 cultures (29.7%), followed by coagulase-negative staphylococci (CONS), mainly *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, in 67 cultures (16.3%).⁴⁴ Notably, neither study provided specific resistance percentages for the identified species. To further investigate bacterial resistance in pediatric patients, a retrospective

chart review was conducted at King Abdulaziz Medical City-Central Region. This study focused on children aged 0-14 years who were admitted for their first documented UTI. The data collected included demographic details, clinical presentations, investigations, and comprehensive information on the isolated bacteria and their AR patterns. The inclusion criteria specified patients aged 0 to 14 years with a discharge diagnosis of UTI, defined by the presence of both $\geq 50,000$ cfu/mL of a single uropathogenic organism and a positive urinalysis (evidenced by at least one of the following: WBC ≥ 5 cells/hpf, positive leucocyte esterase, or presence of bacteria) from a properly collected urine sample. Additionally, patients with a bacterial colony count of 10,000–100,000 cfu/mL, along with urinalysis showing pyuria or bacteriuria, were also considered to have a UTI. The exclusion criteria included patients older than 14 years, those with hospital-acquired UTIs, chronic renal failure, severe urinary tract birth defects (such as cloacal exstrophy), immunodeficiency or immunosuppression, and recipients of solid organ transplants. Among the reviewed cases, 202 children met the inclusion criteria. The most commonly isolated uropathogen was *Escherichia coli*, accounting for 75.7% of the cases, followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* at 9.4%. Overall, 67.5% of the uropathogens exhibited resistance to ampicillin. Specifically, 66.2% of *E. coli* strains are resistant to ampicillin, and 57.1% are resistant to cotrimoxazole.⁴⁵

2.2.4 Bahrain

A retrospective cross-sectional study conducted in Bahrain by Mohammed et al. (2022) aimed to assess the local resistance patterns of the uropathogens responsible for UTIs in hospitalized infants. The study was carried out in the Pediatric Department at Salmaniya Medical Complex and included infants from birth up to 12 months of age, with preterm infants excluded from the analysis. A total of 10 organisms were isolated from 133 positive urine cultures, with *Escherichia coli* being the most frequently identified pathogen, accounting for 66 cases (49.6%). *Klebsiella* was the second most common organism, found in 43 cases (32.3%). The study revealed that *E. coli* presented the highest degree of resistance to cephalosporins, with a resistance rate of 55.5%. Among the cephalosporins, the greatest resistance was observed against cephalothin, a first-generation cephalosporin, with a resistance rate of 54.9%.⁴⁶ Another retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate the prevalence of pathogens isolated from urine cultures in pediatric patients with microbiologically confirmed UTIs and to assess the antimicrobial resistance patterns of these organisms. The study took place in the Pediatric Department of King Hamad University Hospital (KHUH) in Bahrain and focused on children up to 14 years of age. Patients with chronic urinary tract conditions and neurodevelopmental disorders affecting the urinary tract were excluded from the study. Urine samples from 624 pediatric patients were analyzed, with 60 patients excluded on the basis of the exclusion criteria. Among the remaining cases, 242 (42.9%) had positive cultures, defined as bacterial growth exceeding 105 colony-forming units (CFU)/ml of a significant pathogen. The cases were divided into three age groups: neonates (<28 days), infants (28 days to one year), and children (one

year to 14 years). The study identified 25 different bacterial species as the causative agents of UTI, with *Escherichia coli* being the most prevalent at 68.6%, followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* at 10.3%. *E. coli* was the leading cause of UTIs across all age groups, with the highest frequency observed in infants (75%), followed by children (69.52%) and neonates (64.71%). The study also revealed that *E. coli* exhibited the highest resistance to cefazolin (94%), followed by ampicillin (62.68%). In contrast, *E. coli* showed the greatest sensitivity to nitrofurantoin (98.96%) and amikacin (98.43%). Among the *E. coli* cases, 23.49% (39 out of 166) were identified as extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL)-producing strains. The ESBL-producing *E. coli* strain showed the highest resistance to ampicillin (100%) and cefazolin (100%).⁴⁷ In addition, a prospective study conducted at Bahrain Specialist Hospital over five years further supported these findings. This study analyzed 1,146 isolates from pediatric patients aged 0-14 years, with samples including urine cultures, urethral swabs, stool samples, eye swabs, and throat swabs. Streptococcus Group A (52.98%) and *Escherichia coli* (35.97%) were the most frequently observed microorganisms. Streptococcus Group A strains were resistant to erythromycin (13.85%) and clindamycin (9.18%), whereas *E. coli* strains were significantly resistant to trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (22.97%) and amoxicillin/clavulanic acid (20.19%).⁴⁸ A further retrospective analytical study conducted by Al Romaihi et al., 2018 at the Primary Health Center, Salmaniya Medical Complex, focused on investigating antimicrobial resistance in uropathogens among patients visiting primary health centers. This study aimed to evaluate the AR patterns of common urinary pathogens to guide the selection of appropriate empirical treatments for uncomplicated community-acquired UTIs via local data. The research included outpatients who were clinically suspected of having UTIs by their physicians and subsequently underwent urine culture tests. Significant bacteriuria was defined as the presence of more than 10^5 colony-forming units (CFUs) per milliliter of urine. Patients were categorized into four age groups: 0–14, 14–18, 19–64, and 65 years and older. Among pediatric patients aged 0–18 years, *Escherichia coli* emerged as the most commonly isolated pathogen, followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *E. coli* demonstrated low sensitivity to cephalothin, whereas *Klebsiella* spp. exhibited particularly low sensitivity to nitrofurantoin.⁴⁹

2.2.5 Qatar

A retrospective cohort study utilized routinely collected hospital data from febrile infants over a 12-month period, focusing primarily on patients at Hamad General Hospital's inpatient pediatric unit and the El-Sad Centre, the largest emergency facility in Qatar. Out of a total of 8,237 pediatric admissions, 459 infants met specific inclusion criteria. These criteria were designed to identify febrile infants showing signs indicative of a UTI who had undergone urine sample collection for microscopy and culture prior to the initiation of antibiotic therapy. The inclusion criteria required positive findings for pyuria and bacteriuria on urine microscopy, as well as positive leukocyte esterase and nitrites on a urine dipstick test. Additionally, the study required culture results that met defined thresholds for a UTI, specifically more than 50,000 colony-forming units per millilitre (cfu/mL)

in catheterized samples or any bacterial growth in samples obtained via suprapubic aspiration. Infants who had received antibiotics before urine sample collection were excluded to avoid the risk of false-negative results. Furthermore, cases where urine microscopy did not reveal pyuria or bacteriuria, as well as samples collected via a urine bag rather than a catheter, were excluded because of concerns about contamination and the reliability of the results. Among the uropathogens isolated, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were the most common, accounting for 79.7% and 9.8% of those in the ESBL group and 57.2% and 18.7% of those in the non-ESBL group, respectively. However, importantly, no AR testing was conducted for the bacteria isolated in this study.⁵⁰ Additionally, a study conducted by Maisa et al. (2022) at Hamad Medical Corporation (HMC) in Qatar focused on invasive Group B streptococcal (GBS) bloodstream infections in both pediatric and adult populations. The study defined invasive bloodstream infection (BSI) as the presence of at least one positive blood culture for GBS in patients exhibiting signs of infection. For patients with persistent BSI caused by the same organism, only the initial episode was included in the prevalence analysis. However, if a patient experienced multiple BSI episodes during the same hospital admission, only the first infection was considered for prevalence, whereas subsequent episodes were included in the assessment of microbiological characteristics and clinical outcomes. Among the 200 identified GBS-positive patients, 4 were excluded because they did not meet the inclusion criteria (specifically, positive cerebrospinal fluid with negative blood cultures). Children and adult patients were categorized into different age groups. Patient demographics, microbiological data, and clinical characteristics, including outcomes, were collected via the Electronic Hospital Information System (HIS). The study revealed that pediatric patients aged 4 years and younger accounted for 35.7% (70/196) of the cases, with the majority being neonates (39 cases, 59%) infected within the first 7 days of life. The age group of 5–14 years accounted for just 1.02% (2 cases) of the total. The analysis revealed that GBS isolates presented significant resistance, with 51% (100/196) showing resistance to erythromycin, followed by resistance to clindamycin.⁵¹ Another study sought to profile the phenotypic resistance of *Salmonella* strains to relevant antibiotics within the pediatric population. This research involved the collection of 246 *Salmonella* isolates from children under the age of 18 who were admitted to the Pediatric Emergency Center at Hamad Medical Corporation (HMC). Among these isolates, 220 (89.4%) were obtained from stool samples, and 26 (10.6%) were isolated from blood samples. The study revealed that 30.4% of the *Salmonella* cases among Qatari patients were caused by typhoidal *Salmonella* strains, accounting for 28 cases. In contrast, nontyphoidal *Salmonella* strains were more prevalent, representing 64.6% of the isolates, with 159 cases identified. The AR profile revealed that the highest resistance rate was to tetracycline, with a resistance rate of 23.9%, followed closely by that to ampicillin, which had a resistance rate of 21.1%.⁵² A comprehensive retrospective cross-sectional study was undertaken by physicians at the Primary Health Care Corporation (PHCC) in Qatar, with a focus on the clinical data of 181 pediatric patients diagnosed with otitis media (OM). These children, ranging in age from 1 to 18 years,

underwent ear cultures to identify the causative organisms. The study specifically excluded cases involving patients over 18 years old with discharged OM and those who had received antimicrobial treatment within 7 days prior to the collection of specimens, ensuring that the data accurately reflected the bacterial landscape without recent antibiotic interference. The findings of the present study revealed that *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was the most frequently isolated pathogen, accounting for 27.6% of all cases. In addition to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Haemophilus influenzae* emerged as the second most commonly isolated organism, identified in 13.3% of the cases. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* exhibited reduced sensitivity to ciprofloxacin, with an 88.2% sensitivity rate. In contrast, *Haemophilus influenzae* exhibited significant resistance to cotrimoxazole, with 33.3% of the isolates being resistant.⁵³

2.2.6 Iraq

A retrospective analysis at Hevi Pediatric Teaching Hospital in Duhok, Iraq, examined sepsis in children using data from 1,098 blood samples collected over four years from 3,865 patients aged 1 day to 15 years. Patients were admitted to PICU, NICU, or semi-intensive care units based on clinical signs of sepsis. Of the samples, 520 (47.35%) showed positive microbial growth. A decline in sepsis rates was noted during the COVID-19 pandemic. Gram-positive infections were more prevalent, accounting for 74.75% of isolates (379 cases), compared to gram-negative bacteria. Coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) were the most common gram-positive organisms (264 cases, 52.07%), followed by methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) in 45 cases (8.88%). Among gram-negative isolates, *Klebsiella* spp. was most frequent (55 cases, 10.85%), followed by nonlactose fermenters (42 cases, 8.28%) and *Escherichia coli* (29 cases, 5.72%). Importantly, antimicrobial resistance testing for antibiotics was not conducted as part of this study.⁵⁴

Additionally, a study conducted by Salman et al. (2021) investigated urinary tract infections (UTIs) in children in Baghdad. The study analyzed 302 urine samples from children aged 6 months to 12 years attending three pediatric hospitals. Of these, 299 samples (99%) showed bacterial growth. Gram-negative bacteria predominated (267 cases, 89.29%), with *E. coli* accounting for 56% and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* for 14%. Among gram-positive isolates (32 cases), *Enterococcus faecalis* was the most common (62.5%), followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* (37.5%). Antibiotic susceptibility testing revealed 100% resistance of all gram-negative isolates to cefixime. In addition, all *Enterococcus faecalis* strains were fully resistant to penicillin.⁵⁵

Another study focused on imipenem resistance among pediatric patients at the Central Pediatric Teaching Hospital in Baghdad. Researchers collected 100 clinical samples (blood, urine, wound swabs, and sputum) from children aged 1 day to 15

years between October 2020 and August 2021. The most frequently isolated imipenem-resistant organisms were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (21 cases) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (19 cases). *K. pneumoniae* was primarily found in younger children (1 day to 3 years), particularly in urine samples from UTI cases.⁵⁶ Furthermore, a prospective observational study conducted at the Central Teaching Hospital of Pediatrics in Baghdad involved 573 febrile children aged 1 month to 18 years presenting to the emergency department between January and June 2017. Children with prior antibiotic use or urological conditions were excluded. Among the collected urine samples, 116 (20.24%) tested positive for bacterial growth, with infections more common in females (73 cases, 27.7%) than in males (43 cases, 13.9%). UTIs were most frequent in infants under 1 year of age (25 cases, 30.8%). *E. coli* was the most commonly isolated pathogen (73 cases, 54.9%), followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (17 cases, 12.8%). *E. coli* isolates showed a high resistance rate to ampicillin (91.7%), while *K. pneumoniae* was completely resistant to both ampicillin and cephalothin (100%).⁵⁷

2.2.7 Oman

A prospective cohort study was conducted at the Royal Hospital in Oman, focusing on oncology patients aged 13 years or younger who were hospitalized between January 2015 and October 2017. Among the 100 patients included in the study, 74 positive bacterial blood culture results were identified in 38 patients, yielding a positive blood culture rate of 51%. The study revealed that gram-negative organisms were more prevalent, comprising 57% (n = 42) of the total isolates. *Klebsiella* species were the most frequently isolated gram-negative bacteria, accounting for 21% (n = 9) of the cases, followed closely by *Pseudomonas* species at 19% (n = 8). Gram-positive bacteria were also significant, with *Staphylococcus* species being the most common, representing 35% of the cases, followed by *Streptococcus* species at 16%. The findings revealed that 33% (n = 14) of the gram-negative organisms were resistant to at least four different antimicrobial agents, indicating particularly high resistance to beta-lactam antibiotics, even when these agents were combined with beta-lactamase inhibitors. Furthermore, approximately 31% (n = 13) of these organisms were resistant to piperacillin-tazobactam, and 21% (n = 9) were resistant to amoxicillin/clavulanic acid. The resistance rates among gram-positive bacteria were also alarmingly high across all antimicrobial groups tested, including beta-lactams, aminoglycosides, sulfonamides, and clindamycin. Notably, this study did not conduct individual antibiotic susceptibility testing for each bacterial species. As a result, specific resistance patterns or sensitivities to particular antibiotics for each species have not been determined.⁵⁸ Furthermore, a study was conducted to evaluate the prevalence and characterization of gastrointestinal (GIT) bacterial pathogens and their AR patterns among patients in Oman attending Sultan Qaboos University Hospital (SQUH). This research was carried out in the clinical microbiology laboratory at SQUH. Over the course of the study, which spanned from June 1st to November 30th, 2019, a total of 790 fresh stool samples were collected from patients exhibiting gastrointestinal symptoms. The patients' ages ranged from less than 1 year to 92 years.

Notably, the highest incidence of GIT infections (24 patients) was observed in the 0--10 year age group, with *Salmonella* spp. being the most frequently associated pathogen. *Salmonella* spp. exhibited a significant level of resistance to amikacin (91.9%).⁵⁹ Notably, there is a lack of sufficient research on pediatric bacterial resistance in Oman, especially for studies conducted after 2015.

2.2.8 Kuwait

A study conducted in Kuwait aimed to determine the bacterial profiles and AR patterns in febrile children with bacteraemia. Blood samples were collected at admission from children up to 12 years of age, with the majority being from infants (37, 40%) and newborns (13, 14%). The primary infection sites were the lower respiratory tract, genitourinary tract, and gastrointestinal tract. *Streptococcus pneumoniae* was the most common pathogen (16, 16.7%), followed by *Escherichia coli* (12, 12.5%). The study was segmented into four periods to observe changes in bloodstream infections over time: A (2015–2016), B (2017–2018), C (2019–2020), and D (2021–2022). With respect to bacterial resistance, *Escherichia coli* has low susceptibility to ampicillin (18%), whereas *Streptococcus pneumoniae* remains susceptible to the tested antibiotics.⁶⁰

2.2.9 Other Arab Countries

There is a notable absence of thorough research on the most common bacteria affecting pediatric patients in Lebanon, Jordan, Yemen, and the UAE, especially from 2015--2024. This lack of data underscores the critical need for updated and extensive studies to gain a better understanding of bacterial prevalence and resistance patterns in children. Such research would be invaluable in refining treatment protocols, shaping public health strategies, guiding vaccine programs, and optimizing healthcare resource distribution. Moreover, addressing bacterial resistance in pediatric populations is essential for contributing to global initiatives aimed at combating the growing threat of antimicrobial resistance.

Table 1: Prevalence of bacterial pathogens and AR patterns among pediatric populations in the Middle East. Data were collected from 2015 to 2024. (NA: Not applicable)

First author, year	Country	Type of study	Settings	Age	Samples	Most common bacterium	Highest bacterial AR
Fares Kahal, 2023 ³²	Syria	Retrospective observational cohort study	Damascus Hospital	3 h to 13y	Different sites	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Nalidixic acid & Norfloxacin
Fares Kahal, 2022 ³³	Syria	Cross-sectional descriptive retrospective study	Al Mujtahid Hospital	3 h to 13y	Different sites	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone, and Trimethoprim
Ayat Abbood, 2022 ³⁴	Syria	NA	Laboratory	0 h to 18y	Urine	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Cefotaxime, Cefuroxime, Norfloxacin, & Imipenem
Rama Jadeed, 2021 ³⁵	Syria	Prospective	Children's University Hospital	0 h to 13y	Different sites	Klebsiella	NA
Diana Kassem, 2017 ³⁶	Syria	NA	Galilee Medical Centre	0 h to 17y	Different sites	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NA
Nancy Attia, 2023 ³⁷	Egypt	NA	Alexandria, Egypt Hospital	NA	Different sites	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Cefadroxil, Ceftriaxone, & Cefepime
Mahitab Hussein, 2023 ³⁸	Egypt	Cross-Sectional Study	Children's Hospital, Ain Shams University	1 m to 13y	Swab (cough or endotracheal tube aspirate)	Klebsiella pneumonia	Amikacin
						<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	Cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone Cotrimoxazole
Ahmed Gaballah, 2022 ³⁹	Egypt	NA	El Shatby University Hospital, Mabart al Asafra Hospital, and Damanhur	NA (neonates)	Blood sample	Klebsiella pneumonia	Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid and Ampicillin/Sulbactam
						<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Ampicillin

			General Hospital			Enterococcus Spp.	Cefoxitin
Naema Elseady, 2021 ⁴¹	Egypt	Retrospective	Children's Cancer Hospital of Egypt	3 m to 18y	Blood samples	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ampicillin
						<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	Benzylpenicillin
John Labib, 2018 ⁴⁰	Egypt	Prospective observational study	Cairo University Children Hospital	1 m to 12y	Blood urine and sputum cultures	Klebsiella	Quinolones
Fajr Saeedi, 2024 ⁴⁴	Saudi Arabia	Retrospective cross-sectional	King Abdulaziz University Hospital	< 18	Different sites	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	NA
Mohammed Alsubaie, 2023 ⁴²	Saudi Arabia	Retrospective study	King Abdulaziz University Hospital	0 m to 14y	Urine culture	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ampicillin
Omar Alzomor, 2019 ⁴³	Saudi Arabia	Retrospective matched case-control study	King Fahad Medical City	≤17	Different sites	Klebsiella pneumonia	NA
Hameed Tahir, 2019 ⁴⁵	Saudi Arabia	Retrospective chart review	King Abdulaziz Medical City-Central Region	0-14y	Blood and Urine analysis	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ampicillin
Deena Mohammed, 2022 ⁴⁶	Bahrain	Retrospective cross-sectional	Salmaniya Medical Complex	0-12 m	Urine sample	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Cephalosporins
Omaima Shaaban, 2021 ⁴⁷	Bahrain	Retrospective cross-sectional	King Hamad University Hospital	≤ 14 y	Urine sample	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Cefazolin
Kasim Ardati, 2021 ⁴⁸	Bahrain	Prospective study	Bahrain specialist hospital	0-14y	Different sites	Streptococcus Group A	Erythromycin
						<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Trimethoprim/sulfa methoxazole

Ebrahim Al Romaihi, 2018 ⁴⁹	Bahrain	Retrospective Analytical Study	Primary Health Center, Salmaniya Medical Complex	0-18y	Urine samples	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Cephalothin
Mohammad Qusad, 2024 ⁵⁰	Qatar	Retrospective cohort study	Hamad Medical Corporation & El-Sad center	0-12 m	Urine & blood samples	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NA
Maisa Ali, 2022 ⁵¹	Qatar	Retrospective study	Hamad Medical Corporation	0-14y	Blood sample	Group B streptococcus	Clindamycin
Sara Al-Hadidi, 2021 ⁵²	Qatar	NA	Hamad Medical Corporation	2-18y	Stool and blood culture	Salmonella	Tetracycline
Qasem Buhaibeh, 2019 ⁵³	Qatar	Retrospective cross-sectional	Primary Health Care Corporation	1-18y	Ear culture	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Ciprofloxacin
Delveen Ibrahim, 2024 ⁵⁴	Iraq	Retrospective analysis	Hevi Pediatric Teaching Hospital	0-15y	Blood sample	Coagulase-negative staphylococci	NA
						Klebsiella	
Hamzah Salman, 2022 ⁵⁵	Iraq	NA	Child's Central Teaching Hospital, Kadhimiya, and Al-Elwea Maternity Hospital.	6 m-12y	Urine sample	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Cefixime
						<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	Penicillin
Abdul-Mohammed Al-Rawazq, 2022 ⁵⁶	Iraq	NA	Central Pediatric Teaching Hospital	1d-15y	Different sites	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Imipenem

Noor Al-Khannaq, 2020 ⁵⁷	Iraq	Prospective observational study	Central Pediatric Teaching Hospital	1 m-18y	Urine sample	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ampicillin
Abeer Battashi, 2022 ⁵⁸	Oman	Prospective cohort study	Royal Hospital	≤13	Blood sample	Klebsiella	NA
						Streptococcus	
Asma AlSalmi, 2021 ⁵⁹	Oman	NA	Sultan Qaboos University Hospital	0-10y	Stool sample	Salmonella spp.	Amikacin
Khalifa Al Benwan, 2023 ⁶⁰	Kuwait	Retrospective observational cohort study	Al-Amiri Hospital	0-12y	Blood sample	Streptococcus pneumonia	-(Susceptible)
						<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ampicillin
Sadaf Moghaddam, 2024 ²⁶	Iran	Retrospective study	Children's Medical Center Hospital	NA	Blood sample	Pseudomonas spp.	NA
						Coagulase-negative staphylococci	Penicillin
Davood Kheirkhah, 2023 ²⁷	Iran	Cross-sectional study	Kashan Shahid Beheshti	NA	Urine sample	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ampicillin
Mansoor Kodori, 2020 ²⁸	Iran	Cross-sectional study	Tehran Pediatric Central Hospital	NA	Sputum culture	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Gentamicin
Mohammad Hosseini, 2019 ²⁹	Iran	Descriptive cross-sectional	Alzahra Hospital Tabriz	Neonates (full term: up to 28 days) (Preterm up to 8 weeks)	Different sites	Coagulase-negative staphylococci	Cotrimoxazole and Amikacin
						Acinetobacter	Ciprofloxacin

				old; 56 days)			
Yakup Cag, 2021 ³⁰	Turkey	NA	Kartal Dr. Lutfi Kirdar Training and Research Hospital	0-17y	Urine sample	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Ampicillin
Nadide Sav, 2021 ³¹	Turkey	Retrospective study	Pediatric Nephrology Clinic	1-17	Urine sample	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NA

3 Conclusion and limitations

This study revealed the high prevalence of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* among children in the Middle East, with *E. coli* showing widespread resistance to ampicillin. These findings highlight the urgent need for antibiotic stewardship, improved infection control, and new antibiotic development to combat the rising threat of AMR in the region. Addressing factors such as inappropriate antibiotic use and inadequate healthcare infrastructure is crucial for improving outcomes. Despite the fact that this study provides insightful information about the patterns of bacterial resistance in the Middle East, there are several key limitations. First, the analysis dataset was restricted to research performed between 2015 and 2024, which may not fully capture long-term trends or recent developments in bacterial resistance. Furthermore, variations in research methodology, sample size, and data reporting among different countries could have created discrepancies, which could have affected the comparability of findings. Third, this study primarily depended on published data, which may have excluded unpublished research or specific local resistance patterns that could affect the overall outcome.

4 Future directions

Several areas for further research can be suggested. First, genomic studies should be undertaken to pinpoint specific genetic markers linked to AR in bacterial strains from the Middle East. This approach would offer crucial insights into resistance dynamics, aid in identifying emerging patterns, and help target treatments. Future research should also explore innovative methods to improve antibiotic use in both hospital and community settings, as well as assess the effectiveness of existing

antibiotic stewardship programs in the region. Additionally, collaborative regional studies involving countries with limited data on pediatric AR would enhance our understanding and support the creation of targeted interventions. Finally, it is essential to develop and implement new antibiotic treatments that correspond to the resistance patterns identified in the Middle East and to investigate the impact of alternative therapies, such as probiotics and bacteriophages, on reducing AR. This would ultimately improve patient outcomes in the Middle East and address the global challenge of antimicrobial resistance.

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